

Spectrophotometric studies on tributyl tin chloride and butyl tin trichloride with PAN [1-(2-pyridyl azo)-2-Naphthol], Quinalizarin (1-2-5-8-tetrahydroxy anthraquinone), and Alizarin red-S [Sodium salt of (1, 2 dihydroxy-3-anthraquinone) sulphonic acid].

S. B. SAXENA and (K_M) CHHAYA SAXENA

Post Graduate Department of Chemistry, Madhav Institute of Technology & Science, Gwalior-474005

Manuscript received 14 October 1976, accepted 23 August 1977

Tributyl tin chloride and butyl tin trichloride form red, reddish pink and yellowish orange complexes with PAN, Quinalizarin and Alizarin red-S respectively. The complexes with PAN [1-(2-pyridyl azo)-2-Naphthol] and Quinalizarin (1-2-5-8 tetrahydroxy anthraquinone) exhibit maximum at 540nm and with Alizarin red-S-(Sodium salt of 1, 2-dihydroxy-3 anthraquinone sulphonic acid), the complexes show the maximum at 475nm.

The composition of the complexes in all the cases is 1 : 1 as determined by Mole Ratio method and Job's Method of continuous variation employing spectrophotometric data.

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC studies of the chelates of transition metals and rare earth metals in solution have been studied in detail by a large number of workers in recent past^{1,2}. The stability constant, structure and the composition of the chelates have been determined by using Slope ratio, Mole ratio and Job's method of continuous variation. In the field of organometallic complexes such studies are rare. It may be probably due to the fact that such compounds undergo ready hydrolysis in aqueous solution. It has been observed that certain dyes do yield coloured organotin chelates in solution and their stability constants have been determined spectrophotometrically. Irving and Cox⁴ reported the interaction of triphenyl tin chloride with dithiozones and extracted the complexes in carbon tetrachloride. Work on the chelates of organotin compounds with diphenyl carbazones⁵ have also been studied colorimetrically. Pilloni⁶ has shown by spectrophotometric measurements that the complexes of R_2Sn^{+2} (R = Me, Et, Bu and Ph) with 1-(2-pyridyl azo)-2-Naphthol (PAN) are highly soluble in dioxan and the stability of these complexes decreases in the order of Ph > Bu > Et > Me. Di-ethyl-tin compounds in the concentration range of 2×10^{-6} , 2×10^{-4} M are shown to yield 1 : 1 complexes with 4-(2-pyridyl azo) resorcinol (PAR)⁷. It is therefore worthwhile to extend the above investigation in solution and the authors have made a detailed investigation of the following system using 95% ethanol as a solvent.

Experimental

Doubly distilled ethanol (95%) was used as a medium throughout these investigations and absorbance measurements were made on Beckmann D.B. double beam spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched fused silica cells at a fixed temperature of $35 \pm 1^\circ$.

All the dyes used in the present investigation form colloidal electrolytic solution and therefore extremely dilute solution in the concentration range of 10^{-8} M and 10^{-4} Molar were prepared in doubly distilled ethanol. Stock solutions of 1×10^{-2} M concentration of ligands and the Lewis acids were also prepared in the same solvent. For spectrophotometric investigations these solutions were diluted with ethanol and used.

Composition of the Complex :

The composition of the complexes was determined by Mole ratio method⁸ and Job's method of continuous variation⁹.

(I) Mole Ratio Method :

In this method the spectrophotometric titration

of solution of fixed concentration of ligand PAN, Quinalizarin and Alizarin Red-S with varying amounts of Bu_3SnCl and BuSnCl_3 solutions was performed as follows.

Thus a fixed volume (3.0 ml.) of ligands (for PAN $2 \times 10^{-4} M$, Quinalizarin $.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ and Alizarin Red-S $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) were mixed with increasing volumes (0.5 ml. to 6.0 ml.) of the solutions of Lewis acids (e.g. $\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn}^{+1}$ and BuSn^{+3} of $2 \times 10^{-4} M$, $.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution for PAN,

Quinalizarin and Alizarin Red-S respectively). The total volume in all the cases was made up with ethanol to a constant volume (10.0 ml.). The absorbance of these solutions were measured at wavelength of maximum absorption for the complexes. The results are shown in Fig. 1.

(II) *Job's Method of Continuous Variation* :

In Job's method of continuous variation the concentration of both the reactants is varied. All the systems were examined by this method also.

Fig. 1. Spectrophotometric Titration (Mole Ratio Method)
Plot of Lewis Bases against Lewis acids e.g. Tributyl Tin Chloride and Butyl Tin Trichloride

- 540 nm [□-□] $\text{BuSnCl}_3/\text{PAN}$
- 540 nm [○-○] $\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}/\text{PAN}$
- 540 nm [⊕-⊕] $\text{BuSnCl}_3/\text{ALIZARIN RED-S}$
- 540 nm [●-●] $\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}/\text{ALIZARIN RED-S}$
- 475 nm [△-△] $\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}/\text{QUINALIZARIN}$
- 475 nm [○-○] $\text{BuSnCl}_3/\text{QUINALIZARIN}$

Fig. 2. Job's method of continuous variation. Plot of Lewis bases against Tributyl Tin Chloride and Butyl Tin Trichloride

□-□—BuSnCl₃/PAN]-540 nm
 ⊙-⊙—Bu₃SnCl/PAN]-540 nm
 ⊕-⊕—BuSnCl₃/ALIZARIN RED-S]-540 nm
 ●-●—Bu₃SnCl/ALIZARIN RED-S]-540 nm
 △-△—Bu₃SnCl/QUINALIZARIN]-475 nm
 ○-○—BuSnCl₃/QUINALIZARIN]-475 nm

The stock solutions of Bu₃SnCl & BuSnCl₃ and ligand were diluted to $5 \times 10^{-5} M$ for PAN, $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ for Quinalizarin and $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ for Alizarin Red-S complexes. Thus solutions containing varying amounts of Lewis acids Bu₃Sn⁺ & BuSn³⁺ (0.00 to 10.0 ml.) of requisite concentration were mixed with (10.0 to 0.00 ml.) of equimolecular solutions of ligands. The absorbance of series of solutions so made was measured at the wavelength of maximum absorption. The results are depicted graphically in figure 2.

Colour of the Complex :

When the ethanolic solution of dye is added to the solution of Bu₃Sn⁺ or BuSn³⁺, the specific changes in colours are summarised in Table-1.

Effect of Time on Colour of the Complex :

The colour was instantaneously produced and there was no change in the absorbance even after 24

hrs. The order of mixing of the reagent also had no effect in the absorbance value.

Effect of Temperature :

Variation of temperature had no effect on colour of the complex. Determinations were made at a temperature $35 \pm 1^\circ$. Large variation of temp. is expected to effect the results.

Results and Discussion

(a) System Bu₃SnCl, BuSnCl₃/1-(2-pyridyl azo)-2-Naphthol

The data as collected by the above two methods suggest formation of 1:1 complex. The rare possibility of existence of charged complexes in nonaqueous solvents and well established action of PAN^{10,11,12} behaving as tridentate ligand leads to the suggestion that in the initial stages the complex mostly exist in the following A-form which is

TABLE I

Absorption in 95% ethanol for the ligands and their organotin complexes				
Ligand	Lewis acid	max nm	max $\times 10^{-4}$	Colour
PAN	X	480	.066	Yellow
PAN	Bu ₃ Sn ⁺	540	.31	Red
PAN	Bu Sn ⁺ ²	540	.283	Red
Quinalizarin	X	510	.68	Light Violet
Quinalizarin	Bu ₃ Sn ⁺	540	1.12	Reddish Pink
Quinalizarin	Bu Sn ⁺ ²	540	1.2	Reddish Pink
Alizarin Red-S	X	480	.148	Light Yellow
Alizarin Red-S	Bu ₃ Sn ⁺	475	.203	Yellowish Orange
Alizarin Red-S	Bu Sn ⁺ ²	475	.303	Yellowish Orange

neutral and it contains hepta-coordinated tin atom with two-five membered rings and this may be in equilibrium with the structure B.

Although it is not certain yet, which of the two structures should be stable and under what

condition. Further work in this direction is necessary. Apparently at low pH values species A is likely to be more stable while at higher pH species B may be expected to be more predominant. Thus there seems to be pH dependence in the stability.

(b) System Bu_3SnCl , $BuSnCl_3$ /Quinalizarin and Alizarin Red-S

The above data is in confirmity with 1 : 1 complex, it is not possible to suggest unambiguous structures in the above two cases with the help of the collected data. There are two possibilities of chelation.

The chelation can occur from the quinonoid oxygen and the adjacent phenolic oxygen or with the two adjacent phenolic oxygens. The two alternative arrangements are shown by Fig. C and Fig.D respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. T.N. Srivastava, Professor, Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow for his encouragement and guidance. One of the authors (Km. Chhaya Saxena) is thankful to C.S.I.R. for awarding a junior research fellowship.

References

1. K. C. SRIVASTAVA and S. K. BANERJI, *Austr. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 1385.
2. K. C. SRIVASTAVA and S. K. BANERJI, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1968, **38**, 327.
3. S. S. MISHRA and J. P. TONDON, *Bull Acad. Pol. Sci. Ser. Scs. Chem.*, 1970, **18**, 425.
4. H., IRVING, and J. J. COX, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 1470.
5. R. T. SKERL, and G. E. BRICKER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **33**, 428.
6. G. PILLONI, *Anal. Chem. Acta.*, 1967, **37**, 497.
7. G. PILLONI and G. PIAZZOGNA, *Anal. Chem. Acta.*, 1966, **35**, 325.
8. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Industr. Eng. Chem. Analyt.*, 1944, **16**, 11.
9. P. JOB, *Ann. Chem.*, (Paris), 1928, **9**, 113.
10. D. BETTER-IDGE, Q. FERANDO and H. FRERIS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 294.
11. A. CORSINI, I. MARLING YIH, Q. FERANDO and H. FRERIS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 1090.
12. W. J. GEARY, G. NICKLESS and F. H. POLLAND, *Anal. Chem. Acta.* 1962, **27**, 71.